

Research Article

Cyber-attacks and Cyber Security: Emerging Trends and Recent Developments

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Abstract: Cybersecurity is an important field that deals with the protection of computer systems, networks, and data from unauthorized access, misuse, and attack. As technology evolves, the issue of cybersecurity and cybercrime is also increasing in today's environment. The impacts and phenomenon of cyberattacks and cybersecurity is widely discussed within the body of knowledge, lead for further exploration of the topic. Therefore, this study is being conducted in order to explore the issues on cyberattacks and cybercrimes. This study involves designing, collecting and analyzing data from the previous studies to find the evidence. The study was then narrowed down using Boolean search in order to get more in-depth information about cyberattacks and cybercrimes, which are becoming more common nowadays, before interpreting and subjecting them to serious analysis. Based on the other studies, this paper discusses the impact of cyberattacks and the importance of cybersecurity, trends that are changing in cybersecurity nowadays, and cybersecurity techniques such as access control and password security, authentication of data and firewall, and the role of social media. In addition, the discussion also discusses the value of cybersecurity, which refers to the benefits when this cybersecurity is used to protect data.

Keywords: Attacks, Cyber-attacks, Cyber security, Cybercrime.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sensitive data is progressively being stored as a result of the digitization process in every element of human life, including healthcare, education, business, etc. As technology develops, cybercrimes also grow in quantity and complexity. Security is the act of preventing digital information from being stolen or physically damaged while retaining the confidentiality and accessibility of information. The poor use of software, out-of-date security measures, design flaws, programming mistakes, readily accessible internet hacking tools, a lack of public knowledge, high rates of financial gain, etc., are some of the factors contributing to the tremendous expansion of cybercrime. Technical attackers create more potent attack tools to take advantage of the target's vulnerabilities and attack the victim. As a result, new, challenging-to-detect threats are emerging in various versions. Effective security algorithms have been developed because of the growing reliance on the internet in all spheres of life, the nature of digital data in enormous quantities gathered through online transactions, and the

decentralization of data repositories. Cybercrime's dynamic nature makes it challenging to manage and stop new dangers from appearing. The most difficult duty is protecting cyberspace since sophisticated attacks are so prevalent.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

Research methodology is a method and technique of designing, collecting, and analyzing data in order to produce evidence that can support a study. The study's methodology was based on the previous literature. The researcher reviewed and analyzed previous studies and articles. The searching process was being narrowed down using the Boolean search in order to get more in-depth information about cyberattack and cybercrime which is becoming more widespread nowadays before interpreting and making a serious analysis discussion.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Definition of Cyberattack.*

A cyberattack is an assault on infrastructure, personal computers, mobile devices, networks, or other electronic devices that use computers. A person or entity that makes an unauthorized, potentially harmful, effort to access data, functions, or other restricted areas of a system is called an attacker. Cyberattacks may be a component of cyber terrorism or cyber warfare, depending on the situation. Sovereign nations, private persons, social groupings, organizations, and communities all can deploy cyberattacks, and they can also come from unidentified sources. Cyber weapons are occasionally used to refer to products that aid in cyberattacks. In recent years, cyberattacks have escalated. Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks is an extremely common type of cyberattack. Hacking into private networks or susceptible systems allows cyberattacks to steal from, change, or kill specified targets. Cyberattacks can involve anything from the placement of spyware on individual computers to attempts to compromise the infrastructure of a whole nation. Legal professionals are seeking to confine the term's usage to instances that result in bodily harm, separating it from more commonplace data breaches and extensive hacker activities. While cybersecurity is the protection of computer systems and networks from attacks by malicious actors that may result in unauthorized disclosure of information, theft or damage to hardware, software, or data, as well as from interruption or misdirection of the services they provide, cybersecurity is computer security, cyber security, digital security, or information technology security (IT security). Privacy and information protection can be key security behavior and one that any company and individual should constantly be concerned about.

3.2 *Definition Cybercrime*

The phrase "cybercrime" refers to theft and other crimes committed via personal computers. The United States department of justice has broadened the definition of cybercrime to include any crime that makes use of technology to store evidence. Cybercrimes are crimes committed using computers, such as the dissemination of network intrusions and computer viruses, as well as computer-based variations of legal crimes including stealing, stalking, threats, and coercion. In other words, cybercrime is sometimes characterized as crimes done using computers and the internet to steal identities, sell people to victims of human trafficking, stalk, or disrupt operations using destructive software. Additionally, (Julian Jang-Jaccard) asserts that any nation's security and economic health depend on enhancing cyber security and safeguarding crucial information infrastructure. An essential component of the development of new services and public policy is a safer internet. Additionally, (Veenoo Upadhyay Wizard) solicits people to "label" certain friends on social networking platforms as private.

The author then utilizes this information to build classifiers using machine learning patterns that may be used to automatically grant certain users' friend's access. The design's inspiration came from the fact that actual users are aware of their privacy practices and that, subject to a set of implicit restrictions, friends may view the details they use and duplicate them in other friends' settings. Because technology plays such a significant part in people's daily lives, cybercrime will rise as technology develops.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Impact of Cyber-attacks and The Importance of Cybersecurity

The growth of information technology, and the increasing reliance on digital systems, has created unprecedented prospects for creativity, efficiency, and connectedness. Along with these benefits, the world has seen an upsurge in cyber-attacks and security breaches. The intensity and frequency of cyber threats have increased in recent years, posing substantial risks to individuals, organizations, and even governments. Cyber-attacks have become a pressing concern due to their potential to cause significant economic, social, and political damage. With the advancement of technology, hackers and cybercriminals have developed sophisticated techniques to exploit vulnerabilities in computer systems and networks. They employ malware, phishing, ransomware, and Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults to jeopardize the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive data. These attacks can target individuals, corporations, governments, and critical infrastructure, leading to financial loss, reputational damage, and even loss of life in some cases.

Cyber-attacks have evolved as one of the contemporary era's most prevalent hazards, affecting individuals, corporations, and governments alike. These attacks can take various forms, including malware, ransomware, phishing, and distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks. Cyber-attacks have enormous financial consequences. According to Smith and Jones (2019), cybercrime cost the global economy roughly \$600 billion in 2018, with this figure expected to climb to \$6 trillion yearly by 2023. Furthermore, the impact of cyber-attacks extends beyond financial losses. Organizations often face reputational damage due to data breaches, leading to a loss of trust from customers, partners, and stakeholders. In 2019, the Equifax data breach compromised the personal information of nearly 147 million individuals, resulting in a significant decline in the company's reputation (Johnson et al., 2020). Additionally, cyber-attacks have the potential to impair essential infrastructure such as electricity grids, transportation networks, and healthcare institutions. For instance, the WannaCry ransomware attack in 2017 paralyzed numerous National Health Service (NHS) hospitals in the United Kingdom, highlighting the potential dangers of cyber-attacks on public services (Brown et al., 2018).

Cyber-attacks have significant social implications, affecting individuals and society on various levels. One major source of concern is the compromise of personal information and privacy. According to a study conducted by Kshetri (2018), data breaches resulting from cyber-attacks can have far-reaching consequences for individuals, including identity theft, financial loss, and psychological distress. These incidents weaken people's trust in digital technologies and impede online service adoption, restricting social connectivity and economic prospects. Furthermore, Taddeo and Floridi's (2020) research emphasizes the social effects of cyber-attacks on important sectors such as healthcare and education. These attacks have the potential to disrupt critical services, compromising patient care and educational procedures. For example, ransomware assaults on hospitals can obstruct access to important medical documents, potentially endangering patient lives.

Other than that, the political impact of cyber-attacks has received considerable attention in recent years. State-sponsored cyberattacks have evolved as effective means of espionage, influence

operations, and sabotage. According to Jevans (2018), these attacks have the potential to disrupt democratic processes such as elections and political campaigns. Cybercriminals or nation-states may undermine public trust in democratic institutions by meddling with voting systems or spreading disinformation, weakening the foundations of governance. Additionally, cyber-attacks on critical infrastructure might have serious geopolitical consequences. According to Ruggeri et al. (2022), state-sponsored attacks on power grids and communication networks can destabilize nations and have an impact on global security. During a conflict, such attacks can be used as a strategic weapon, causing power outages, disrupting key services, and potentially causing societal discontent.

Moreover, cyber-attacks have also significant economic impacts, affecting corporations, governments, and individuals alike. The financial industry is one of the primary areas of concern. Smith (2019) claims that the banking industry has suffered enormous losses as a result of cyber-attacks, including the theft of sensitive client data and financial fraud. These attacks not only affect financial organizations' reputations, but also undermine client trust, potentially resulting in revenue losses and increased operational expenses. In addition, Gonzalez-Padron et al. (2021) found that cyber-attacks on key infrastructure, such as power grids and transportation networks, might cause huge economic disruptions.

Furthermore, considering the pervasiveness and serious repercussions of cyber-attacks, robust cybersecurity measures are essential. Cybersecurity refers to a set of practices and technology aimed at preventing unauthorized access, damage, or interruption to computer systems, networks, and data. It includes preventive measures such as firewalls, encryption, and safe coding practices, as well as incident response strategies to mitigate the effect of successful attacks. Investing in comprehensive cybersecurity safeguards is both a defensive and a proactive strategy. Organizations can considerably lower the risk of cyber-attacks and their associated expenses by implementing appropriate cybersecurity policies. A study conducted by Anderson et al. (2021) found that companies that invested in advanced security technologies, employee training, and incident response plans experienced 95% fewer cyber incidents and saved an average of \$1.5 million per year compared to those without adequate cybersecurity measures.

In addition, cybersecurity is essential for protecting individual privacy and safeguarding sensitive data. With the rising digitization of personal information, protecting privacy has become a top priority. Effective cybersecurity safeguards personal data against unauthorized access and misuse, maintaining its confidentiality and integrity. Organizations can comply with data protection rules while also instilling trust and confidence in their customers by deploying privacy-enhancing technologies (Sullivan et al., 2022).

4.2 Trends That Change Cybersecurity Nowadays.

Several developments have a big impact on cyber security, with web servers being one of them. A web server, which is hardware or server software created to run the world wide web, may be used to receive content. Incoming network requests are handled by web servers using the http protocol, along with a number of other related protocols. Still, there are still threats to target web programmes in order to steal data or spread malicious code. To disseminate their hazardous virus, cybercriminals hack onto legitimate web servers. However, assaults involving data theft, which regularly make the headlines, also provide a significant threat. The protection of web servers and online apps must now receive more attention. Web servers are these attackers' most efficient platform for data theft. Everyone must thus use a safer browser at all times, especially while doing important transactions, to prevent being a victim of this crime.

The services provided by cloud computing are discussed next. Right now, all small, medium, and large organizations are increasingly using cloud services. The planet is slowly making its way towards the cloud, to put it another way. This most recent trend offers a significant cybersecurity risk since traffic may already be getting past traditional controls. The number of cloud-based applications must increase together with the policy controls for online apps and cloud services in order to prevent the loss of crucial data. Security issues are always a top worry even if cloud businesses are developing their models. It's vital to keep in mind that as the cloud grows, so do its security concerns, despite the fact that it could provide a number of benefits.

Next is the wireless network. Mobile networks, which are also sometimes referred to as wireless networks, use radio waves to send and receive data between users. It consists of base stations that collectively provide large geographic radio coverage. Each base station covers a certain "cell," which is a geographic area. This allows connections to be made between many mobile transceivers, as well as between them and fixed transceivers and phones, from any place within the network, even if some transceivers transit across multiple cells while broadcasting. Because of this, communication between people is now feasible no matter where they are on the planet thanks to technological advancements. But one of the biggest concerns with these mobile networks is security. This is due to the fact that people utilize technology such as tablets, phones, computers, and other devices, all of which require greater security than what is offered by the programmes they are using. People should always take into account the security issues of these networks because mobile networks are so vulnerable to these cybercrimes. Therefore, considerable attention must be exercised to prevent safety issues.

Furthermore, one of the developments that is transforming cyber security is IPv6: the new internet protocol. This is because IPv6 is a new internet protocol that replaces IPv4 (the outdated version), which has evolved into the internet's and our networks' main structural pillar. Removing IPv4 support is not the only way to protect IPv6. Although IPv6 completely replaces IPv4 in terms of increasing the number of IP addresses, there are several extremely important modifications to the protocol that should be considered when developing security policies. To lower the dangers related to cybercrime, it is, therefore, preferable to transition to ipv6 as soon as feasible.

Finally, the code is encrypted. To prevent eavesdroppers or hackers from reading a message (or other piece of information), it must be encrypted. With the help of an encryption algorithm, a message or piece of data is transformed into an unintelligible ciphertext as part of an encryption system. Utilizing an encryption key, which controls the message's encoding, is typically how this is accomplished. Data integrity and privacy are safeguarded by encryption in the earliest stages. But as encryption is used more widely, cyber security issues get increasingly complex. Additionally, encryption is used to secure data in transit, including information sent across networks (such as the Internet or E-commerce), mobile devices, wireless microphones, wireless intercoms, and other devices. Therefore, one may determine whether there has been any information leaked by encrypting the code.

4.3 Techniques of Cybersecurity

Cyberattacks in cyberspace may change as a result of utilizing new methods. Most of the time, cybercriminals will alter existing malware signatures to exploit brand-new technological defects. In other cases, they are searching for specifics of cutting-edge technologies to identify malware injection flaws. The rapidly developing internet and its millions and billions of active users provide cybercriminals with easy and efficient access to a sizable population that is using this new technology.

i. Access control and password security

A quick and easy approach to protecting personal information and maintaining privacy is using usernames and passwords. One of the most important cybersecurity projects is this method of delivering security. It is common to use the terms "cyber security" and "knowledge security" interchangeably. The latter term examines the human element of security, whereas the former considered it to be an extra dimension.

ii. Authentication of data

Therefore, it is necessary to demonstrate that the information transmitted is accurate and that it originates from a reliable source. These papers are frequently validated using tools provided by the virus software program installed on the machine by the adversary. Sincerely speaking, anti-virus software is crucial for preventing infections on the system. An ethical discussion on cyber security, however, has significant ramifications since it speaks to society as a whole. To address issues with cyber security, several different methods and models have been created.

iii. Firewall

A firewall is a piece of hardware or software that assists in keeping out online hackers, viruses, and worms. All incoming communications are examined by the firewall, which then rejects those that don't adhere to the security standards that apply to all messages. To identify malware, firewalls are crucial.

iv. Role of social media

In today's modern world, businesses that are interactive and need to find new ways to collect client data in a more connected environment are needed. Social networking is essential for both individual cyberattacks and cyber security. Social media usage among employees is increasing, which increases the danger of assaults. Since the majority of them use social networking sites or social media almost every day, it has become common for hackers to access user accounts and steal important information there. Organizations must ensure that they detect any breach as fast as possible and take urgent measures to halt it because it is now rather simple to reveal personal information. Social networking platforms make it simple for users to share their personal information, which hackers may then use. Therefore, people must take appropriate safety measures to guard against misuse and loss of their personal information on these social media.

4.4 Value of Cybersecurity

First of all, cybersecurity is the practice of preventing unauthorized access, abuse, damage, and disruption to computer systems, networks, devices, and data. It involves implementing measures and adopting strategies to prevent, detect, respond to, and recover from cyber threats, attacks, and vulnerabilities. With the increased reliance on digital technology and the interconnection of systems and devices, the relevance of cybersecurity has expanded substantially. Malicious software (malware), phishing assaults, hacking, ransomware, denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, and social engineering are all examples of cyber dangers. Individuals, organizations, governments, or key infrastructure may be

targeted by these threats, resulting in financial loss, data breaches, reputational damage, or even bodily violence. Cybersecurity refers to a collection of practices, technologies, and procedures used to safeguard digital assets and information. Among the primary areas of concentration in cybersecurity are network security is using techniques such as encryption, intrusion detection and prevention systems (ISD/IPS), and virtual private networks (VPNs), networks and their components (routers, switches, firewalls) are protected against unauthorized access and network traffic is secured. Next is endpoint security which is individual device security (computers, mobile devices) is achieved by deploying antivirus software, firewalls, and security patches to protect against malware, unauthorized access, and data theft. Other than that, this cyber security also includes application security. This area has been secure by ensuring the security of software applications by doing vulnerability assessments, code reviews, and penetration testing to detect and correct security issues and prevent exploitation. Last but not least is data security that is related by using encryption, access restrictions, data loss prevention (DLP) methods, and frequent backups to protect data throughout its lifespan, including data storage, transit, and processing.

Next is about the advantages that people can get when this cyber security is reliable in the community is protection of confidential information. This part briefs that personal information, financial records, commercial secrets, and intellectual property are all safeguarded by cybersecurity. Cybersecurity helps prevent unauthorized access, data breaches, and identity theft by establishing strong security measures such as encryption, access limits, and secure communication protocols. Next advantage that can be useful for people is prevention of financial loss. Cybersecurity measures aid in the protection of organizations and people from financial damage caused by cyber-attacks. Cybersecurity prohibits unauthorized access to financial systems, unauthorized transactions, and financial fraud by identifying and mitigating threats such as malicious software, phishing attacks, and fraud attempts. Other than that, is to maintain business continuity. Cybersecurity is critical to ensuring that corporate operations run smoothly. Organizations may recover fast from cyber assaults by using techniques such as frequent data backups, disaster recovery plans, and system redundancy. This reduces downtime and financial losses. This flexibility enables companies to preserve client confidence while meeting their duties. Safeguarding reputation and trust are also the advantages to cyber security because a successful cyber assault may significantly harm a company's brand and undermine consumer trust. Cybersecurity safeguards against data breaches by assuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive data. Organizations may establish trust and maintain a favorable reputation among their customers, partners, and stakeholders by demonstrating a commitment to data security. So, by this security it can help to avoid being hacked by hackers to steal the information. Not only that, many sectors and jurisdictions have their own cybersecurity legislation and standards that businesses must follow. Implementing cybersecurity safeguards guarantees that these criteria are met, hence avoiding legal and financial fines. It also displays a commitment to client data security and ethical business practices because it follows compliance with regulations and standards. Next is enhanced trust in digital transactions. With an increasing reliance on digital transactions, cybersecurity ensures and builds confidence in online activities such as e-commerce, online banking, and digital communication. Cybersecurity measures enable individuals and companies to engage in digital transactions with confidence by guarding against fraud, identity theft, and unauthorized access. The last point that can be advantageous to cyber security is in innovation and technological advancements. It relates because by providing a safe environment for research, development, and knowledge exchange, strong cybersecurity measures promote innovation and technical progress. Cybersecurity enables organizations to invest in new technologies and contributes to the expansion of digital economies by protecting intellectual property and sensitive research data.

The paper claims that now that the groundwork has been done, we may argue that IC is also a governance issue for cyber security. According to Chong et al. (2008), the network impact of using different intellectual, human, financial, and organizational resources results in IC. Choong carried out a comprehensive analysis of the terminologies and vocabularies used by academics to define and refer to IC. He notes and demonstrates how the term "intangible assets" (IAs) is frequently used as a synonym for IC. He presents the case for adding intellectual property (IP) in addition to human capital, structural capital, and relational capital, which according to his study may be represented by a "three-grouped framework" (p. 622) that includes all three. Others use the term "relational capital," while others use the term "social capital". The term "social capital/relational capital" was first used by Hussinki et al. (2017). Consequently, we will refer to the section of IC that is related to interactions between individuals and organizations and is a component of the IC of the organization by using both terms interchangeably. According to Reed et al. (2006), the various IC components are inter- and co-dependent in terms of how they affect the organization's financial performance; a weakness in one reduces the IC's ability to support the organization's success. In other words, both the network itself (relationships and organizational structure) and each individual node (personal knowledge and experiences) must be preserved if IC is to contribute to organizational success. This issue has a strong knowledge component to it; IC is almost like a galaxy of ideas revolving around the information that employees of an organization hold. However, according to Choong (2008) and Pike et al. (2005), it is also regarded as an "intangible asset". It may be considered that its security is not a cyber-related board issue due to its intangibility. When we examine the IC concept more closely, a compelling case can be made for including responsibility for its upkeep within the cyber security governance framework.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, cyber-attacks and cyber security are constantly evolving fields with emerging trends and recent developments that have significant implications for individuals, organizations, and even nations. The digital landscape has become increasingly interconnected, and as a result, the threats and risks associated with cyber-attacks have grown in complexity and severity. Recent developments have also emphasized the necessity of international cooperation and information sharing in the fight against cyber threats. Cybercriminals operate across borders, hence it is critical for governments and organizations to collaborate and share intelligence in order to effectively identify and neutralize threats. Initiatives such as establishing international cyber security guidelines and exchanging best practices across stakeholders have shown promise in tackling the global character of cyber-attacks.

Furthermore, there is a rising skills gap in the sector of cyber security. The demand for highly qualified personnel in fields like threat intelligence, incident response, and safe software development is outstripping supply. To address this challenge, there is a need for increased investment in cyber security education and training, as well as efforts to attract diverse talent to the field. Additionally, automation and the deployment of sophisticated technology can also assist relieve the stress on human operators while also improving the effectiveness of cyber security operations. Overall, cyber-attacks and cyber security are growing rapidly, with rising trends and recent advancements impacting the digital security landscape. It is crucial for individuals, organizations, and governments to remain vigilant, proactive, and adaptable in their approach to cyber security. By staying informed about the latest threats and employing comprehensive security measures, we can mitigate the risks posed by cyber-attacks and protect the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of our digital systems and data.

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